

AUTOR /ES – Comunicación A4.33
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TÍTULO
The effect of an adapted Pilates Method program in physical condition and lumbar pain disability on visually impaired elders. A pilot study.
RESUMEN
<p>Background People with visual impairment are associated with worse physical condition and decreased functional capacity affecting daily life activities and functional status. Physical exercise provides benefits in that people such as improving the quality of life, functional capacity, mobility, self-confidence, etc. On the other hand, elderly people suffer from disability caused by lumbar pain.</p> <p>Objective To assess the effects of Pilates Method on functional capacity, disability caused by lumbar pain and physical condition in older adults with visual disabilities.</p> <p>Methods A group of Fundación ONCE with different degree of visual impairment were selected for study with an intervention group of adapted Pilates Method and a control group of breathing and relaxation program following an 8 weekly session program. Senior fitness test¹ was used to test physical fitness improvement and the Oswestry Low Back Pain Disability Questionnaire² and a 10 points scale to assess lumbar pain level, where 0 representing the absence of pain and 10 for unbearable pain. The Shapiro-Wilk test was used to determine the normality of the data. To determine the homogeneity of the sample at the initial evaluation there were used the Student's t test for parametric variables and Mann-Whitney for non-parametric variables. To determine differences in the outcomes over evaluations repeated measured Student's test was applied for parametric variables and Wilcoxon test in case of non-parametric ones. The significance level was set at 5% for the entire statistical analysis.</p> <p>Results No significant differences were found between groups in Oswestry Index and pain scale after intervention program. The strength of upper and lower extremities, flexibility of lower extremities and core; and aerobic endurance improved in Pilates Group but only with only statistically significant in the arm curl right test.</p> <p>Conclusion Eight weekly session of PM improved the strength of upper and lower extremities, flexibility of lower extremities and core; and aerobic endurance in elder with visual impairment, although just significantly in strength upper extremities</p> <p>References 1. Rikli RE, Jones CJ. Functional Fitness Normative Scores for Community-Residing Older Adults, Ages 60-94. <i>J Aging Phys Act.</i> 1999;7(2):162-181. doi:10.1123/japa.7.2.162 2. Page SJ, Shawaryn MA, Cernich AN, Linacre JM. Scaling of the revised Oswestry low back pain questionnaire. <i>Arch Phys Med Rehabil.</i> 2002;83(11):1579-1584. doi:10.1053/apmr.2002.34604</p>